

CONSTRUCTION DRAWING. CONTENTS OF CONSTRUCTION DRAWINGS. NAME AND MARKING OF CONSTRUCTION DRAWINGS. THEIR SCALE AND CONSTRUCTION ELEMENTS.

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Annotatsion: Agricultural buildings - buildings where livestock and poultry are kept, buildings for the repair and storage of agricultural machinery, warehouses and buildings where products are stored, and the like; engineering structures - bridges, tunnels, road overpasses, embankments, various hydrotechnical and earth structures, blast furnaces, reservoirs and the like.

Keywords: Residential and public buildings, which are collectively referred to as civil buildings, such buildings include residential buildings, dormitories, clubs, hospitals, schools, various administrative buildings and the like; industrial buildings factories, factory buildings and other production buildings, power plant, steam room and similar buildings.

The content of construction drawings and the method of their formalization, the scales and conventional symbols used in the drawings depend on the type of construction objects, as well as the purpose of the drawings. Various construction objects - buildings and structures can be divided into the following four main groups according to their function:

- residential and public buildings, these are summarized under the general name - civil buildings, such buildings include residential buildings, dormitories, clubs, hospitals, schools, various administrative buildings and the like;

- industrial buildings - factories, factory buildings and other production buildings, power plant, steam room and similar buildings;

- agricultural buildings - buildings where livestock and poultry are kept, buildings for the repair and storage of agricultural machinery, warehouses and buildings where products are stored and similar;

- engineering structures - bridges, tunnels, road overpasses, embankments, various hydraulic and earth structures, blast furnaces, reservoirs and the like.

Depending on the type of objects to be depicted, construction drawings can be divided into architectural-construction drawings - drawings of residential, public and industrial buildings, and engineering-construction drawings - drawings of various engineering structures designed to perform various technical tasks.

- the most advanced method of construction is assembling (assembling) buildings and structures from factory-made elements and details. Typical industrial products are brought ready-made from factories and factories to the construction site, where they are assembled using lifting cranes. In the design of buildings and structures, the necessary structural elements and details are selected according to the catalog of typical industrial products, and the signs (brands) of these products are placed in the drawings and assembly schemes.

Construction works are divided into general construction and special works. General construction works include all works on the construction of the building itself (including

finishing works), and special types of construction works include water supply and sewage, heating and ventilation, gas supply, electrification, telephone, landscaping. works on Depending on this division of construction works, the working drawings are divided into separate parts or sets. Each such set is given a special mark (sign) and this mark is placed in the main record of each drawing in these sets. The brand is formed from the initials of the name of this part of the project.

The mark placed on the drawing consists of a letter indicating which set of the project working drawing this sheet belongs to and the order number of this sheet. For example, the mark AR-6 indicates that this sheet belongs to the set of working drawings "Architectural-construction solutions" and its sequence number is 6, and the mark KJ-11 refers to the set of working drawings "Reinforced concrete structures" and the sheet number is 11 and so on.

The number of working drawings of different brands also includes assembly drawings, in which simplified images show the mutual arrangement of assembled elements and the brands of some elements are placed.

Drawings intended for the preparation of construction co-instructions in factories and construction sites are called preparation drawings.

During the construction of buildings and structures, sometimes the layout of rooms is slightly changed or one structure is replaced by another. In such cases, these changes are introduced in the corresponding drawings or the drawings are redrawn. Drawings that fully reflect the layout of the rooms of the completed building, its dimensions and construction structures are called execution drawings. Drawings drawn in actual measurements are called measurement drawings.

Fig. 1. Structural elements of a load-bearing wall building

1 - foundation, 2 - inclined pavement, 3 - plinth, 4 - load-bearing wall, 5 - inter-floor covering, 6 - attic covering, 7 - curtain wall, 8 - supporting rafter, 9 - roofing sheet, 10 - podkos, 11 - column, 12 - hatch, 13 - attic, 14 - mauerlat, 15 - peremichka, 16 - stairs, 17 - kosour, 18 - staircase, 19 - drum

Depending on the type and size of construction materials, buildings are made of small blocks and granular elements (small wall blocks, stones, grooved peremichka and kosours, etc.) It is divided into large block and large panel buildings.

In large-block buildings, the outer and inner walls between the windows and peremichkas are made of large blocks, and the covering and roofing material falls on these blocks..

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